

MYTHOLOGICAL UNITS IN ENGLISH FICTION AND THE ISSUES OF
TRANSLATING THEM INTO UZBEK

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Annotation: *This article is devoted to the application of mythological units in English literary texts and the problems of translation of myths in Uzbek language. The connection between myth and literature is one of mutual dependence, as myth is integral element of literature, as a result while translating literary works it can be found mythologemes as well and their translation should be adequate to the source language. Translation is briefly defined as the result of linguistic-textual operation in which a text in one language is re-contextualized in another language. As a linguistic-operation, translation is however, subject to and substantially influenced by a variety of extra-linguistic factors and conditions.*

Key words: *myth, mythology, culture, literary translation, untranslatability*

One of the everlasting mysteries of translation is transplant of the source values to the target culture. It becomes possible in the course of creative efforts of the Translator who surmounts challenges of the untranslatable. Mythology has been always placed among those challenges and never is entropy so intensive as in texts associated with mythological images and ideas. On the one hand, it may seem easy to transliterate or loan mythic names and thus introduce them into the target

cultural use. But the borrowed signs turn out to be malicious shape-shifters and begin to live on their own in the foreign environment.

Literary translation focuses on the artistic value of the original text. In this case, translation becomes an artistic activity. Thus, the translation of a literary text or a poem is very different from the translation of a scientific text because the creative element is an essential thing in the translation of a poem but it is not in the scientific text. Willis (1996) proposes that the most creative translator is the one who possesses a creative mind which is part of the translator's intelligence. Thus, translation creativity is more prominent in literary translation than any other text type especially poetry which is considered as being a treasure of figurative, rhetorical and aesthetic language which is highly and intricately sensitive, effective and rich with all kinds of implications, associations, connotations and emotions. So, the translator of literary texts is free, more creative and less direct when he tends to translate literature in general and poetry in specific. Hence, the literary approach emphasizes on the talent of enriching a text when translating it which needs the mastering of different skills starting by the reading skill passing by the understanding of the text and ending by the linguistic talent.

Literature is representative of a nation's culture and, it is the culture that determines the motifs and beliefs behind the literature and myth of a society. Due to the vast scope of differences between cultures, there are barriers and problems during the process of translation that some of them may even lead to untranslatability. In translating myth works, especially English myth, motifs, and cultural issues are very different from their Uzbek counterparts. Accordingly, it is appropriate to study the historical roots of mythological images, to make a comparative analysis of their mythological and historical features on the basis of folklore and written sources so that sometimes translation of mythologemes is sometimes becomes a problem, and translators tries to find equivalent for this units. For example, in English culture has some specific characters such as, "fairy", "gnome" and "redcap". Their translation in Uzbek language "pari", "gnom" and

“redcap”. This mythological units are unfamiliar for the Uzbek culture so in translation of myth-based texts translators gives definition of this images.

In literature, the diversity of meaning or the lack of exact correlation and figurative means make the task of literary translation significant. Thus, this kind of translation is recognized as a dynamic and problematic process of translation in culture-bound discourse that needs attention both in linguistic and cultural aspects. During translating a literary work, some factors cause to misinterpret of the authors or devalue their literary works; such as lack of adequate knowledge and prejudice of translators. A literary translator should know both source language and culture and also target language and culture completely. As Larsen (1998), stated that two criteria are necessary to produce a good translation: an adequate knowledge of the source language (ST) and an adequate command of the language into which one is translating that is target language (TL).

The translation is inevitable to communicate inter-culturally and inter-lingually. Newmark (1988), defined culture as the way of life and its manifestations that are peculiar to a community that uses a particular language as its means of expression. Thus, each language group has its own culturally specific features. Since the cultural meanings are steeped in the language, the knowledge and ability of the translator are significant to capture the cultural concepts and cast them in the target text. A translator should be aware of the two cultures to understand the original meaning and transfer it within the counterparts of the target culture and language.

Discussing the issue of untranslatability, Anthony Pym differentiates between “the basic narrative and definitional structure of the myth” (Pym, 1998). This is a valuable idea to apply to studying informational challenge that any myth presents in translation. Mythical values, images, ideas and events are deeply rooted into the cultural traditions of a people, perceived as a part of the whole and, apart from scholars, without explanation. For a native, a myth is a true (or imaginative) narrative that does not require any definitions and is accepted as a traditional value

rendered by a long chain of narrators. Perhaps it is this value that makes myth wholly or, at least, partly untranslatable. As soon as the myth, clad in the dress of another language, appears in the context of another culture it loses its natural valuable structure first of all due to the losses of information, in other words, it suffers intensive entropy, which predicts all kinds of misinterpreting.

Myths present the spiritual or religious life aspects of a nation. They refer to the symbolic beliefs of a typical society in history. Therefore, they are considered complex cultural phenomena. Newmark (1991), pointed out that a word is essentially a cultural memory in which the historical experience of the society is embedded. Therefore, in the myth which embodied the related historical and cultural features of a nation, transferring the lexical and symbolic structures of the original text is considerable.

For instance, in the process of translating a English mythic novel into Uzbek, the translator is faced with two main challenges: firstly, translator should deal with the concept and lexicon in SL, which require an understanding of English culture and mythology, and secondly, the translator should take TL meaning equivalent of an item in SL, include features absent in TL culture. Thus, myth translation does not have the problem of finding just equivalent but interpreting a text encoded in a semiotic system. Utilizing cultural equivalents requires knowing the differences and similarities between the cultures and cultural implications. The choices made by the translators as the decision whether to keep stylistic features of the source language text or whether to keep the figurative language of the original become considerable in the case of myth translation.

The untranslatability always exists in a myth text since its features are rooted in the culture and language. The more differences between SL and TL, the more untranslatable aspects occur. Therefore, untranslatability happens when the translator translates the cultural concepts to the SL while there is no equivalent cultural issue in the TL. Lotfipour (2015), stated that translation of literary discourse in the sense of exact meaning transferring and effect of author's cultural

intention was really testing or even impossible. He believed that cultural factors always become a barrier in translation, and often the translators face untranslatability.

The function of translation as a mediator in cross-cultural communication is to introduce one culture to another. Cultural aspects always have been the obstacle against translation procedures. Sometimes these obstacles result in untranslatability during the process of cross-cultural communication and translation. Myths are considered one of the most important literary genres by many literary critics. Scholars define myths as tales believed as true, usually sacred, which set in the distant past or other worlds with extra-human, inhuman, or heroic characters. e, the cultural gap between English and Uzbek leads to untranslatability and inadequacy of translation in the case of mythic novels. But the translator can compensate for this gap by studying more about the background of the original text.

THE LIST OF USED LITERATURE:

1. Willis (1996), A framework for task-based learning, The university of Michigan, Longman.
2. Larsen (1998), Meaning based-translation: Guide to cross-language equivalence, University of Richmond, Virginia
3. Newmark, P. (1988). A textbook of translation (Vol. 66). New York: Prentice hall.
4. Anthony Pym(1998), Method of translation, First edition, Routledge, Manchester St.Jerome
5. Lotfipour. K. (2015). Suggestions toward Some Discourse-Analytic Approaches to Text Difficulty: With Special Reference to" T-Unit Configuration" in the Textual Unfolding. Iranian Journal of Language Teaching Research, 3(1), 1-18